

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES

UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

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Title: Appraising a Higher Education Institution's Waste from Electronic and Electrical Equipment (WEEE) Management Practices: Towards a Sustainable Plan for Mitigating Risks

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Abstract

Educational institutions heavily depend on EE, particularly on Information Communication and Technology (ICT) equipment and other electronic devices to enhance teaching and learning (Dayaday & Galleto, 2022; Iyer, 2018). However, when these devices reach their end-of-life, they become obsolete or fall out of use, they transform into e-waste – a significant and rapidly growing waste stream worldwide that demands urgent attention. E-waste is classified as hazardous waste and poses risks to both human health and the environment if not properly managed and disposed of. To address critical issues, it is imperative to formulate and implement a sustainable e-waste management plan. The researchers made use of data-gathering methods including survey questionnaires, interviews, document reviews, and observations. To formulate the sustainable e-waste management plan the researchers (a) gathered information on the types and quantities of e-waste generated by the institution in a year; (b) reviewed current inventory practices on e-waste collection and disposal procedures; (c) assess stakeholders' awareness level regarding e-waste management; (d) identify existing initiatives related to e-waste within the institution; (e) employ descriptive statistics and content analysis to analyze the collected data; and (f) crafted a sustainable management plan to serve as blueprint for implementation. The plan included guidelines and policies for proper e-waste handling and disposal. It also includes the economic benefits of e-waste, such as recycling e-waste materials, contributing to environmental protection and financial sustainability. By implementing the e-waste management plan, it can help mitigate risks associated with improper e-waste handling, safeguard human health, and protect the environment.

Introduction

A. Short Introduction

According to Shield (2020), e-waste is the fastest-growing trash stream and the source of invisible waste in the world. E-waste is commonly called WEEE which

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means waste from electric and electronic equipment (*Electronic waste (e-Waste)*, 2022). E-waste not properly handled and disposed of harms the health of humans and animals and the environment. The metals and plastic materials in which these electronic devices are made when improperly dismantled, burnt, or disposed of may cause cancer, kidney failure, heart attack, neurologic sickness, and other illnesses. It may also be a source of air, water, and land pollution. These are the reasons for categorizing e-waste as a form of hazardous waste.

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the Philippines according to Dayaday and Galleto, Jr. (2022), procure ICT equipment to improve and enhance teaching and learning delivery making them one of the e-waste generators. Televisions, laptops, computers, printers, LCDs purchased for teaching and learning or for classroom and office use. Electronic equipment such as these, aids the teachers, students and employees to be more productive. Households and the different sectors which include Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) are contributors to e-waste. HEIs purchase computers, laptops, televisions (TVs), printers, projectors or Liquid Crystal Displays (LCDs), scanners, air conditioners (ACs), electric fans, shredders, and other electronic devices utilized for educational and office purposes. As a result, there is a need for HEIs to implement an e-waste management plan for the effective and efficient disposal of e-waste (G. Dayaday & A. Galleto, Jr, 2022; Iyer, 2014, Mor et al., 2021). HEIs purchase ICT equipment to comply with the requirements of the different stakeholders which may even include regulatory and accrediting bodies. After the ICTs end of life these are replaced for upgrades because of obsolescence due to new software and hardware requirements and or standards required by the curriculum. As a result of these, HEIs become generators of e-waste.

To address issues on e-waste, and to protect human life and the environment an e-waste management plan is imperative. It is everyone's social responsibility to contribute to the realization of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) also known as global goals. The development and implementation of an e-waste management plan is a realization of SDG 12 which encompasses responsible consumption and production and SDG 11 entitled sustainable cities and consumption. SDG 11 and 12 combined, these aim to provide a safe, resilient and sustainable cities through the implementation of waste management and the impact of production on the environment as in the case of producing electronic and electrical equipment to disposal because of obsolescence (<https://www.globalgoals.org/goals>).

B. RRL and RS of Major Concepts

What is e-waste?

E-waste is anything with electronic circuits and electrical parts with a battery, electric cord, or plug that has been discarded with no intent of reuse or that it reached

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the end of its life or obsolescence (Forti, V., Baldé, C.P., Kuehr R., and Bel, G., 2020; Argosino, 2022). These are obsolete, out-modeled non-working, end-of-life electronic products, and equipment for disposal. Household and office appliances such as televisions, refrigerators, washing machines, rice cookers, electric fans, computers, printers, shredders and other electronic/electrical devices that are not being used and/or not functioning are considered e-waste. Gadgets such as mobile phones, laptops, tablets, chargers, remote controls, busted lamps, spent batteries, and other unwanted electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) or products, including broken electronic cigarettes or vapes and worn-out electronic toys are also considered e-waste (Argosino, 2022; *Electronic Waste (e-waste)*, 2023). In summary, all electronic and electrical equipment and gadgets discarded, unwanted, obsolete, out-modeled, and non-functioning are considered e-waste.

In 2019, according to the study by Forti, V., Baldé, C.P., Kuehr R., and Bel, G., (2020), the global e-waste produced is 53.6 million metric tonnes (Mt) which is projected to reach seventy-four (74) Mt by 2030 making it the fastest-growing domestic waste. Asia on the otherhand, contributed the highest amount of e-waste. The Philippines is one of Southeast Asia's top e-waste generators contributing 3.9 kg of e-waste per capita (*The Philippines: making money making e-waste safe*, 2022). In 2019 the total generated e-waste in the Philippines is 32,664.41 metric tons. Realizing the negative impacts of not properly disposed e-waste the Department of Environment and Natural Resources-Environmental Management Bureau (DENR-EMB) launched several initiatives for the safe and responsible disposal of e-waste ("*DENR-EMB Pushes for Safe, Responsible e-Waste Disposal*", 2023 October 20).

Sources of e-waste

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), millions of electrical and electronic devices are discarded yearly. It is now becoming the biggest, largest, most complex, and fastest-growing stream of waste (Shield, 2022). In Asia, the Philippines is one of the largest generators of e-waste (*Electronic Waste(e-waste)*, 2023).

In the study by Forti, V., Baldé, C.P., Kuehr R., and Bel, G., (2020), in 2019 the global e-waste is 53.6 million metric tonnes (Mt) and it is projected to reach seventy-four (74) Mt by 2030 making it the fastest-growing domestic waste. Sources of e-waste according to Celestial (2018), are corporate and household consumers. Corporate includes government, non-government and industry. Discarded household appliances, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) equipment, and small consumer electronic items are sources of e-waste. In the study of Dayaday and Galleto, Jr. (2022), HEIs in the Philippines procure ICT equipment to improve and enhance teaching and learning delivery making them one of the e-waste generators. Electronic ad electrical equipment are purchased for classroom and office use for its day-to-day operations and ultimately to improve teaching and learning. ICT are replaced to upgrade or because of obsolescence due to new software and hardware

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requirements and or standards required by their curriculum. As a result, HEIs contribute to e-waste.

Everyone using electronic and electrical devices is considered an e-waste generator (Celestial, 2018; Alabanza et al, 2022).

Issues and Problems with e-Waste

The increasing number of e-waste generated is attributed to people's high dependency on electronic and electrical equipment, its short life cycles, and limited repair options (*The Philippines: making money making e-waste safe*, 2022; Dayaday M. and Galleto F., Jr.,2022). The continuous technological innovations, consumerism trends, and compatibility concerns are also some of the reasons for the increase in e-waste generated (Nielsen, n.d.).

Impacts of e-Waste

According to Shield (2020) producing electronics involves high levels of hazardous chemicals, greenhouse gases and water drainage. It is made of some parts that are toxic if not properly managed and disposed of that accumulates in soil water and air. It also contains mercury, lead and Brominated Flame Retardants materials that are harmful to humans and animals (*The growing environmental risks of e-waste*, n.d.). Its improper disposal of e-waste affects health due to chemical exposure and environmental degradation (Alabanza, et al. 2022). E-waste when improperly treated, stored, transported or disposed of, or otherwise managed is harmful to human and animals' health and the environment (Celestial, 2018).

Negative impact to human and animals' health

According to Celestial (2018) and Sonny, et al. (2022), e-waste disposed of by open burning, storage, and dumping into landfills releases toxic waste that may be harmful to health. It can be inhaled and ingested orally through contaminated food and water or through direct contact when transporting or dismantling e-waste to extract metals. EE products contain hazardous materials such as metals and chemicals like mercury, lead, beryllium, and barium other persistent organic pollutants that are harmful to both human beings and animals who are exposed to e-waste. These toxic chemicals may cause different skin diseases, neurological sickness, cancer, and heart attacks. In the study of Sonny, et.al. (2022), people and animals living near dumpsites and those that are dismantling or rec e-waste without protective gear suffer from respiratory problems, kidney failure, blood infections, neurological diseases, and congenital diseases. It may even cause stillbirths and abortion. Dismantling which involves de-soldering and removal of chips and circuit boards releases beryllium, dioxins, mercury, and other metals that are harmful to the environment.

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Negative impact on the environment

According to the General Environment Network, e-waste can be toxic, it is not biodegradable and accumulates in the soil, air, and water. Open burning, landfills, desoldering when dismantling, and acid baths cause air pollution when extracting raw materials from e-waste if not properly managed and disposed of causing air, land, and water pollution (*The Growing Environmental Risks of E-Waste*, 2023; Sonny et. al, 2022).

The production of electronic goods also affects climate change since it generates carbon footprints contributing to invisible waste that causes global warming. The manufacture or production of a tonne of laptops, for example, emits 10 tonnes of CO₂.

C. Theoretical Framework

E-waste is the fastest-growing waste stream in the world. If not managed and disposed of properly, its chemical components are toxic and harmful to human and animal health and the environment. Academic institutions are e-waste generators because they depend on electronic equipment used for educational purposes (Dayaday & Galleto, Jr., 2022). As a result of this, an e-waste management plan is important to protect the human populace and the environment from its toxic substances.

e-Waste

e-Waste also known as waste on electronic and electrical equipment (WEEE) is discarded, end-of-life, obsolete, and worn-out electronic equipment. E-waste like any other waste could be managed and disposed of properly because if not, these are harmful to human and animal health and the environment (*EMB: National Policy, Regulatory Framework Already in Place for E-Waste Mngt*, 2020).

Some of the hazardous chemicals from electronic and electrical equipment are lead, mercury, beryllium, Brominated Flame Retardant (BFR), copper, iron, and more. BFR releases dioxins that may be harmful to the human immune system, glucose metabolism, and reproductive system (*E-waste Management Plan*, 2023).

Contributors to e-waste

E-waste comes from households and offices or units from the different public and private sectors which include academic institutions (Celestial, 2018; Sonny et al., 2023). According to the study by (Dayaday, MG and Galleto JR, 2022), academic institutions are e-waste generators because they purchase WEEE such as computers, laptops, printers, televisions, projectors or LCDs, and other electronic equipment for teaching and learning. Academic institutions rely on information communication and technology (ICT) to deliver online and face-to-face instructional delivery. As a result of this, they purchase and upgrade electronic equipment for educational purposes. The electronic equipment and devices purchased will eventually reach

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their end-of-life, will become out-modelled or obsolete, and will be disposed of making it e-waste.

Waste Management

Guidelines on the proper management of waste which include special and hazardous waste are written in Republic Act (RA) 9003 also known as Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000. Its purpose is to ensure the protection of public health and the environment by reducing, reusing, and recycling waste. The RA strongly recommends the systematic administration of ecological waste management which includes segregation, storage, transfer, treatment, and disposal (*Republic Act No. 9003, 2001*). Electronics are categorized under special and at the same time hazardous waste because it is made of toxic materials and metals that when improperly disposed of or handled cause harm to the health and the environment (Alam, 2016). Before RA 9003, RA 6969 was enacted which emphasizes the proper handling, storage, and disposal of toxic metals and chemicals in WEEE. It includes the inventory, monitoring, information, and education of the public regarding the hazards and risks of toxic metals and chemicals (*Republic Act 6969, 1990, EMB: National Policy, Regulatory Framework Already in Place for E-Waste Mngt, n.d.*).

The DENR-EMB introduced various projects and programs to dispose of e-waste safely and responsibly (*DENR-EMB pushes for safe and responsible e-waste disposal, 2023*). The DENR-EMB initiatives include increasing e-waste awareness and responsible e-waste reduction and disposal. To reduce e-waste, they encourage people to trade in their electronic gadgets and identify drop-off points where people can donate or dispose of their e-waste.

In Presidential Proclamation 760 dated May 2014, it was declared that January be a zero-waste month (*Proclamation No. 760, s. 2014, n.d.*). To implement the zero-waste program, the reduce, reuse, and recycle also known as the three (3) Rs of waste management must be practiced. Toxic waste and materials can be avoided and eliminated if it is designed and managed properly with ethics and economics requirements in mind (*Take Steps for Proper Waste Management, 2020*).

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D. Conceptual and Analytical Framework

The study will utilize inventory datasets which include information on the item description, model, serial number, date of purchase, quantity, type, and remarks on electronic equipment. The data sets on the inventory will be used to determine the type and quantity of e-waste generated by the HEI. The researchers will conduct document reviews and observations on existing practices, procedures, and guidelines for the assessment of repairable EE and collection, transfer, and disposal of condemned electronic equipment and assessment for repair. The researchers will likewise adopt the e-waste management questionnaire of the Environmental Information System (ENVIS) Resource Partner Center to determine the knowledge level on e-waste of the identified respondents. This is for the researchers to determine the gaps and include them in the activities that will address the findings. The findings will additionally serve as a guide for the type of educational resources and training that will be included in the plan. The existing solid waste management procedure will be reviewed and analyzed to determine existing practices on collecting, sorting, storing, recycling, and disposal. Existing institutional programs and circulars on waste management will also be gathered to determine interventions that can be added or enhanced. The different e-waste legislation will also be reviewed to determine gaps or inclusions in the e-waste management plan.

E. Purpose of the Study

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This study aims to assess the existing e-waste management practices of a Higher Education Institution (HEI) in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya.

Specifically, this study aims to:

1. gather information on the types and quantity of e-waste generated by a Higher Education Institution in a year;
2. review current inventory practices on e-waste collection and disposal;
3. assess stakeholders' knowledge levels regarding e-waste management;
4. identify existing initiatives related to e-waste within the institution; and
5. craft a sustainable e-waste management plan.

Methodology

A. Design

This study adopt a mixed method, using both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The researchers adopt the e-waste management questionnaire developed by ENVIS RP Centre, NEHU Shillong (Environment Information System, n.d.) since this was already used in another study similar to this. A Likert scale was used to determine the respondents' realization level on matters regarding e-waste on a personal and operational level. The frequency count, percentage, mean and standard deviation were utilized to describe and analyse the responses from the survey questionnaire. The frequency count was used to determine the number and percentage of the same responses. An interview guide was also formulated to gather responses from the identified personnel concerned and other personnel involved in the e-waste management of the institution to discuss procedures that are currently being practiced in the organization. Interview was also used to determine the needs and gaps that they have observed lacking from the the existing procedures. Document reviews were also conducted to determine the amount of e-waste generated in a year, analyse the existing procedures and practices, and determine the existing initiatives on e-waste management, if any.

B. Locale

Saint Mary's University is a premier institution in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya that purchases electronic equipment to achieve its goal of quality education. The university has a basic education and tertiary department. In the basic education, it has a grade school, junior high school and senior high school. The tertiary level has

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four (4) undergraduate schools, a college of Law and Graduate Studies, where students and teachers utilize electronic equipment such as computers, laptops, printers, and many more for teaching and learning. It has three (3) campuses with computer laboratory rooms and lecture rooms with televisions. The library and offices are all equipped with computers, printers, AVR, UPS, and other electronic equipment needed for the day-to-day operation of the institution.

C. Participants and Sample

The participants of the study are the staff of the Inventory and Management Office (IMO), two (2) staff and five (5) Computer Laboratory Technicians Computer and Electronics Technical and Services Office (CETSO), General Services Office (GSO) Head and four (4) staff, twenty-three (23) janitorial services, one (1) Safety and Pollution Control (SPCO) staff and the Vice President for Administration. These participants are chosen because of their involvement in e-waste management in the University.

D. Instrument(s)

A **survey questionnaire** adopted from ENVIS RP Centre, NEHU Shillong (Environment Information System, n.d.) was used to determine the awareness level of the participants and the e current practices on e-waste management of the HEI through the identified respondents. Aside from the survey questionnaire, an **interview** guide was also formulated to describe the existing procedures and practices on e-waste management of the HEI. A list of documents such as inventory, forms for repairs and transfer, and other documents relevant to e-waste management were also gathered for **analysis** to determine the existing procedures, practices, and initiatives. An inventory of the surrendered electronic equipment to the IMO sorted by type and year were also gathered to determine the e-waste generated. The collection and sorting of e-waste was observed to determine the actual practice conducted.

E. Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers secure the permission of the Vice President for Administration before the distribution of the e-waste management questionnaire to identified personnel. Existing documents from concerned offices/units in the HEI, such as inventory reports, written office mandates or objectives, procedures, flowcharts, minutes of meetings with topics on solid waste management, and job descriptions of identified personnel were gathered from the concerned offices to serve as a basis for the description of the current situation of the HEI e-waste management practices. Interviews were also conducted to validate and clarify answers from the survey questionnaire and provide additional information regarding the existing e-waste management and practices.

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F. Treatment of Data

Count and percentage was used to determine the types and quantity of e-waste generated by the institution in a year. The existing inventory practices on e-waste collection and disposal were reviewed and a flowchart was used to analyse the process. Contents of documents, inventory reports, requests, circulars, and relevant communications in the institution were reviewed, compared, and analyzed to determine gaps between existing practices and legislative requirements. The frequency count, percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to determine the knowledge level of respondents and t-test to determine if there is a difference between the knowledge level of the ICT staff with that of the other participants.

The replicability of the research is limited for the reason that the researchers made use of few respondents, particularly those who are directly involved in the e-waste management of the institution, however the survey questionnaire used to gather data was adopted from ENVIS RP Centre, NEHU Shillong (Environment Information System, n.d.) which was used in India

G. Ethical Considerations

The proponents of the research do not have a personal gain on the outcome of the research, nor will she be benefited of its outcome. Although one of the members is from the Computer and Electronics Technician Services Office (CETSO) and the other one is the head of the Inventory and Management Office, they will only benefit from the outcome of the study through the proper handling of the e-waste generated by the institution.

The information gathered from the questionnaire and interviews will not be divulged to parties without interest or are not related to the study. Only the researchers will have access to the responses and information gathered. The questionnaire will not gather the names of the respondents, instead, it will be coded to protect anonymity. The filled-out questionnaire and the transcripts or minutes of interviews will be shredded after the study.

The participants of the study will not be harmed during the collection of data or information needed for the study. They will not be forced to participate as respondents of the study, nor be forced to release information that they think in their capacity will harm them or put them in a difficult situation.

The results of the study will be used to draft an e-waste management policy that will economically, physically, and environmentally help the personnel and the institution. Existing procedures or processes in the handling of e-waste will be improved, thus it will also improve the work condition of the employees directly involved in the handling of e-waste in the institution. The results of the study will be shared and disseminated to the community through the institution's partnership with the Local Government Unit. The respondents/participants of the study, though identified will not receive any compensation and participation will only be voluntary.

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After the approval/clearance from the UREO the researchers started with the data gathering, the proponents of the study will distribute the informed consent to identified respondents. Upon signing the informed consent of the respondents, the proponents started with the distribution of questionnaire, schedule interviews and gather relevant documents for the study.

The outputs of the study will be implemented and owned by Saint Mary's University. The researchers or the proponents of the study will be recognized as the authors.

Results and Discussions

A. Types and Quantity of e-Waste Generated

Based on the inventory report summary for the academic year 2023-2024, a total of nine hundred and ninety-three (993) electronic devices and three hundred and twenty-four (324) electrical devices were procured and utilized to meet various institutional requirements. According to Dayaday and Galleto, Jr. (2022), educational institutions are generators of e-waste because it utilizes ICT for its operations. By utilizing the #WEEE4Future e-waste calculator, the calculated e-waste generated from the acquired electronic equipment amounts to 1,326.01 kilograms (kg), while the electrical equipment contributes 2,268 kgs of e-waste. It is estimated that approximately 480.816 kg of plastic and 42.092 kgs of copper can be salvaged from the electrical devices, potentially saving 2507.7 kg of CO2 emissions when recycled correctly. Similarly, for electronic devices, recycling could recover 35.350 kg of plastic, 38.227 kg of copper, and 49.529 kg of aluminum, leading to a potential reduction of 1,796.278 kg of CO2 emissions.

B. Inventory Practices on e-Waste Collection and Disposal

Based on the interviews conducted and site observations, specific departments are tasked with the collection of electronic and electrical equipment (EE) in need of repair. Electronic gadgets, including desktop computers, printers, keyboards, mice, UPS units, AVRs, and similar devices, are gathered by the CICT Computer and Electronic Technology Support Office (CETSO) while electrical apparatuses are managed by the PPDMO electricians. Both entities utilize their respective service request forms to assess the reparability of the equipment, each having their own separate and unique procedures for repair and disposal.

For repairable equipment, replacement parts are requested from the Purchasing Office. On the other hand, the equipment condemned is turned over to the GTO for disposal. The GTO collects dismantled and sorted parts of irreparable electronic devices from CETSO. Before disposal, the GTO, in coordination with the Internal Auditor, records the number of parts transferred by the CETSO. Unlike electronic devices, electrical equipment is not dismantled and is directly handed over to the GTO for disposal.

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The GTO, through the SPCO, liaises with DENR-accredited waste collectors for proper disposal, though there are times when the GTO relied on nearby junk shops for the collection and disposal of these items. Although there are units in the institution which perform different tasks in handling e-waste, it is recommended that the institution review RA 9003 and RA 6969 which emphasizes proper handling, storage of toxic and chemicals in WEEE. Inventory, monitoring, information and education of the public can be an initiative by the institution to increase awareness of its stakeholders. Moreover, the DENR-EMB projects which include increasing e-waste awareness and responsible e-waste reduction, and disposal could also be considered as a guide for the institution's initiative. Drop-off points can also be copied and replicated as the institution's program.

C. Stakeholders Knowledge on e-Waste

Respondents Profile

Out of the fifteen (15) respondents of the questionnaire, two (2) or 13% are female and the rest are male which constitutes CETSU, IMO, SPCO, PPDMO, GSO, University Learning Resource Center (ULRC) Audio Visual and School of Engineering, Architecture and Information Technology (SEAIT) Laboratory staff. There were five (5) or 33% laboratory technicians, three (3) or 20% are computer technicians, one (1) SPCO Head, one (1) SPCO staff, one (1) IMO staff, one (1) audio visual technician, one (1) GSO, one (1) PPDMO electrician, and one (1) SEAIT Laboratory Assistant. The researchers also interviewed the Vice President for Administration and the GSO Head on matters regarding the institution's initiatives on e-waste. In terms of length of service, one (1) or 6% is with SMU for more than 20 years, three (3) or 20% for 20-15 years, three (3) or 20% for 14-10 years, four (4) or 27% for 9-5 years and four (4) or 27% for 4 years and below.

Knowledge on e-waste management

Table 1.

Questions:	f	%
1. Are you aware of what e-waste is?		
	Yes	14
	No	1
		93%
		7%

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2. How would you rate your knowledge of e waste		
a. I have no idea what e-waste is.	1	6.7%
b. I have heard of the term e-waste but do not know what it is.	1	6.7%
c. I know of the term e-waste but I am unsure of what items fit into that category.	4	26.7%
d. I know of the term e-waste but do not know how it applies to my company.	4	26.7%
e. I know what e-waste is, how items are categorized as such, and that it does apply to certain electronics used by Saint Mary's University.	5	33%
3. Are you aware of the hazards/negative effects of e-waste if it is not handled carefully?		
	Yes 12	80%
	No 3	20%
4. Do you have environmental policies (addressing E-waste) in your workplace?		
	Yes 1	7%
	No 4	27%
	Don't Know 10	67%
5. How does Saint Mary's University deal with its e-waste?		
a. Vendor buyback and exchange	0	0%
b. Sell as Scrap	10	67%
c. Sell as Second hand/ Sell to employees	8	53%
d. Sell to recycling companies	4	27%
e. Recycle	3	20%
Re-Use	2	13%
f. Donate to school / Charity	4	27%
g. Don't Know	0	0%
h. Others (Please Specify) <u>visual aids</u>	1	7%
6. Who is responsible for managing e-waste at Saint Mary's University?		
a. Human Resource	0	0%
b. Office Administration	1	7%
c. Information Technology (IT Department)	4	27%
d. Each unit/department	7	47%
e. Don't know	1	7%
f. Other (Please Specify)	1	7% (GSO)

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7. Is there a proper record of the quantity of e-waste generated and their management measures?	Yes No Don't Know	4 1 9	27% 7% 60%
8. Are there any attempts to minimize the quantity of e-waste generation in your institution/organization?	Yes No Don't Know	4 1 9	27% 7% 60%
9. Are there any provision(s) by the management to have any innovations, or types of equipment in the future to treat the waste generation at the source level?	Yes No	2 13	13% 87%
10. Is there a facility for accumulation and segregation particularly of e-waste through and labeled containers?	Yes No	4 11	27% 73%
11. Did you know that cathode ray tubes and circuit boards are hazardous waste and cannot be disposed of in a landfill due to the presence of toxic substances, such as mercury, lead, and cadmium?	Yes No	14 1	93% 7%
12. Are you aware and following of the Rules and Regulations regarding e-waste management? If No, please specify reason: _not familiar; not yet aware; not yet implemented; no orientation/seminar about this	Yes No	9 6	60% 40%
13. Are you aware of the Four R's (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle and Repair) for e-waste management?	Yes No	11 4	73% 27%
14. Are you aware of the methods to dismantle and recycle e-waste?	Yes No	11 4	73% 27%

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15. How many desktop and/or laptop computers are currently used within your company?		
a. 0-25	2	13%
b. 26-100	1	7%
c. 101-200	1	7%
d. 201-300	0	0%
e. More than 300	9	60%
f. Unknown/do not know	1	7%
16. How often does your company/organization replace desktop computers/electronics devices?		
a. As needed (7)	7	47%
b. Every 1-2 years (0)	0	0%
c. Every 3-4 years (1)	1	7%
d. Others:		
d.1 as long as it is working	2	13%
d.2 7-10 years	2	13%
d.3 10-15 years	2	13%
17. Do you ever interact with electronics and electrical producers regarding exchanges, takebacks, and recycling policies they may follow?		
Yes	2	13%
No	13	87%

Based on the survey results, the majority of respondents are familiar with the concept of e-waste. Most of them are also aware of the four (4) R's (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle and Repair) of e-waste management. This may be the reason, that most of them also know how to dismantle and recycle e-waste. However, it is evident that there are still individuals who remain uncertain regarding the classification of electronic waste (e-waste) and its specific implications for SMU. The majority of respondents are cognizant of the fact that electronic equipment (EE) poses hazards and can yield adverse consequences if mishandled. Notably, only one respondent indicated otherwise. Most of them are aware that e-waste is sold as scrap or sold to employees as second hand.

The results revealed that the majority of respondents are unaware of the the existence of an institutional environmental policy related to e-waste, a situation likely caused by the absence of a formal e-waste environmental policy within the university. Nevertheless, despite the lack of an institutional policy, 60% of respondents reported adhering to e-waste management rules and regulations, while 40% admitted they do not.

When it comes to disposal, most respondents indicated that e-waste collected from various units within the institution is sold as scrap. Functioning electronic equipment (EEs) that have reached the end of their life but can be refurbished are either sold as second-hand items or donated to schools and other units. Additionally,

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some EEs are sold to recycling companies. One respondent mentioned repurposing certain EE components as visual aids for instructional purposes.

In terms of responsibility, most of the respondents answered that EEs are the responsibility of each unit where it was deployed. However, most of the respondents answered that EEs are the responsibility of identified offices, such as IT, department and GSO.

To accurately determine the volume of electronic waste generated, efforts to minimize the quantity produced within the institution, and initiatives by the management to introduce innovations for managing electronic waste generation, a majority of the survey participants indicated a lack of awareness. The majority of respondents also noted the absence of designated facilities within the institution for the collection, storage, segregation, and proper labeling of electronic waste.

In terms of proper recording of quantity of e-waste generated and their management measure, 9 or 60% answered that they do not know while 4 or 27% answered there is none.

The survey results unveiled that the majority of the participants are unaware of the procedures for accurately documenting the quantity of e-waste produced and the corresponding measures for its management. Interestingly, some respondents even indicated a lack of proper documentation practices.

D. Initiatives on e-Waste

While there are existing initiatives on waste management, particularly on hazardous waste, SMU does not have an existing e-waste management plan or other initiatives. At present, there is no separate EE inventory that will make monitoring, control, audit and report of EEE purchased easier.

The CETSU Office, IMO storage room and Gymnasium's basement room serve as temporary storage and collection points of non-repairable or condemned EEs or e-waste for disposal. The GSO Head supervises the collection and transfer of e-waste to the MRU for disposal. Junk shops with certificates from the DENR collects e-waste from the MRU.

The SPCO, on the other hand, has established protocols for overseeing the safe handling and disposal of hazardous waste, encompassing procedures for labeling and disposal, excluding EEEs. Additionally, they extend invitations to various agencies for annual safety and pollution control inspections by government regulatory bodies such as the Bureau of Fire Inspection, Dole, IATF, and DENR-EMB.

E. e-Waste Management Plan

The SMU e-waste management plan was formulated using the findings of the study as a guide. This was submitted to the Vice President for Administration for adoption.

The findings of the study provides a pattern on the awareness, disposal, policy gaps, responsibility, documentation, and initial initiatives which provides a

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structured overview that could guide improvements or policy making. To start with, an e-waste management plan can be used as a blueprint for these.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results of study, the following can be concluded:

- There are two types of e-waste generated in SMU, these are electronics and electrical equipment. At least a thousand of EEs procured in a year can produce at least 3,000 kgs of e-waste. If dismantled properly 500 kgs of plastic and 80 kgs of copper can be recovered from this number of e-waste. If correctly recycled, it can save at least 4,000 kg of CO₂ emissions which causes climate change and global warming.
- There are two distinct offices responsible for repair, recycling and disposal of EEEs each following their own forms and procedures. Each office manages its own inventory and collection. Disposal is condemned or dismantled EE parts are facilitated by the GSO after the inventory done by the the Internal Auditor.
- While most of the respondents know what e-waste is and its four (4) Rs (reduce, reuse, recycle and repair), there is still a few who need to be informed of its classification and implications for SMU. Also most of them lack knowledge or are not aware of the following: (1) determining and documenting e-waste generated, and (2) initiative conducted by the management on introducing innovations to properly manage e-waste generated.
- While there are current initiatives and policies on hazardous waste management, SMU lacks a specific program for managing e-waste and has not yet developed a plan for it.
- There is no designated facility for e-waste collection, storage, segregation and proper labeling in SMU.

Recommendations

- Consider strengthening the institution's awareness by promoting the principles of the reduce, reuse, repurpose, recycle, and repair (5Rs) in the management of e-waste by facilitating seminars, training sessions, programs, and other strategic initiatives.
- Study how the institution can strengthen the coordination of the PPDMO electricians to the CETS0 for a centralized management of e-waste. These two (2) offices could craft procedures and guidelines that will make the management of e-waste easier.
- Consider the inclusion of e-waste management initiatives in the institution's Clean, Healthy, Safe and Friendly (CHSF) program.
- Review and adopt an e-waste management plan for SMU and explore new ways to minimize e-waste to spark future research that will contribute to effective policies and technological solutions.

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- e. Consider studying further the benefits of a centralized facility for collection, storage, and segregation with proper labeling that is compliant to the government standards on e-waste management.

The researchers' main goal is to contribute to the preservation of the environment and mitigation of climate change through research. Guided by this goal, the researchers focused on the electronic and equipment waste because it is a growing concern. Based on the data gathering conducted, the assumptions of the researchers proved true and existing. As a result, the researchers has proven that the e-waste management is needed and the plan would be helpful if realized.

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Appendix A. Photo documentation of SMU e-Waste Management Plan to the VPA

